

TRANSVERSE CRACK GROWTH IN BRITTLE MATRIX HYBRID FIBROUS COMPOSITES.

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Recent analytical work has made it possible to consider the mechanics of the growth of transverse cracks of finite length in a brittle matrix as a function of the physical properties of the component parts of the composite structure. Attention is drawn to the contribution of the matrix work of fracture to crack stability and some preliminary experiments in which this is modified by the inclusion of a second toughening fibrous component are described. The application of this work to practical systems is discussed.

Introduction.

When the failing strain of the matrix of a composite is less than that of the reinforcing fibres multiple cracking of the matrix occurs before the composite fails completely. In the case of an idealised composite consisting of a unidirectional array of continuous fibres loaded in the direction of fibre alignment we have, neglecting any effects due to differences in the Poisson's ratios of the components,

$$\sigma_c = V_f E_f \epsilon + V_m E_m \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where σ_c is the stress carried by the composite at a strain ϵ , V and E refer to volume fraction and Young's modulus and the subscripts f and m refer to fibres and matrix respectively.

The matrix will fail initially at the position of the most severe flaw. If the matrix strain when failure first occurs is ϵ_m^1 we have, just as the matrix fractures:

$$\sigma_c = V_f E_f \epsilon_m^1 + V_m E_m \epsilon_m^1 \quad (2)$$

The load previously carried by the matrix is now transferred to the crack bridging fibres. They will not fracture provided that,

$$V_f \sigma_{f,ult} \geq E_f V_f \epsilon_m^1 + \sigma_m^1 V_m \quad (3)$$

where σ_m^1 is the stress carried by the matrix when it fractures.

As the tensile load carried by the composite is increased the matrix fails at flaws of decreasing severity so that, in the simple system considered, the composite is traversed by an array of parallel matrix cracks. Eventually inequality (3) is no longer satisfied and fibre fracture occurs. The separation of the multiple cracks in the matrix is controlled by the stress transfer between the matrix and the fibres. For cylindrical fibres the distance of separation will lie between x and $2x$ where,

$$x = (V_m/V_f) \sigma_{m,ult} r/2\tau \quad (4)$$

and $\sigma_{m,ult}$ is the maximum stress carried by the matrix when inequality (3) is satisfied, $2r$ is the fibre diameter and τ is the shear strength of the fibre/matrix interface. If the space between the parallel cracks is greater than $2x$ the stress developed in the matrix midway between the existing cracks is sufficient to cause further matrix cracking as the applied load is increased.

The strain energy released during fracture must be at least equal to the energy absorbed during the fracture process. Energy can be absorbed in various ways. Aveston, Cooper and Kelly have considered the case of a unidirectionally reinforced composite under fixed load conditions when the matrix fails at a strain of ϵ_{mu} and the crack extends across the full width of the specimen (1). In these circumstances all the reinforcing members can be assumed to interact with the matrix in an identical manner. Under fixed load conditions, work ΔW is done by the applied stress because the presence of the crack increases the compliance of the composite system. Before differential movement can take place between the elastically extending fibre and the elastically relaxing matrix over the stress transfer length x , energy $G\pi$ per unit area of interface has to be supplied in order to rupture the fibre/matrix bond. This can be expressed as γ_{db} per unit area of crack face. Also frictional energy losses U_s occur as a consequence of the differential movement between fibres and matrix. The matrix loses strain energy ΔU_m as a consequence of its elastic relaxation over the stress transfer length and there is a corresponding increase in the elastic strain energy of the fibres ΔU_f . Further work is done in fracturing the matrix. This can be written γ_m per unit area of matrix fracture surface. The energy absorbed cannot exceed the energy released if a crack is to be formed. Hence for a crack which has extended across the full width of the composite we have,

$$2\gamma_m V_m + \gamma_{db} + U_s + \Delta U_f \leq \Delta W + \Delta U_m \quad (5)$$

The various terms in (5) have been evaluated by Aveston, Cooper and Kelly and are given as,

$$\Delta W = E_f E_m V_m \epsilon_{mu}^3 \alpha r (1 + \alpha)/2\tau \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta U_m = E_f E_m V_m \epsilon_{mu}^3 \alpha r/3\tau \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta U_f = E_f E_m V_m \epsilon_{mu}^3 \alpha r (1 + \alpha/3)/2\tau \quad (8)$$

$$U_s = E_f E_m V_m \epsilon_{mu}^3 \alpha r (1 + \alpha)/6\tau \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma_{db} = 2\sigma_{mu} V_m G/\pi \quad (10)$$

where $\alpha = E_m V_m / E_f V_f$ and σ_{mu} is the stress carried by the matrix when

fracture occurs. Because of the difficulties in estimating G_{π} Aveston, Cooper and Kelly give the following limits between which matrix cracking would be expected; these are,

$$2\gamma_m V_m (1 + \sigma_{mu}/\tau) \leq E_c E_f \epsilon_{mu}^3 \alpha^2 r/6\tau \quad (11)$$

and,

$$2\gamma_m V_m \leq E_c E_f \epsilon_{mu}^3 \alpha^2 r/6\tau \quad (12)$$

Inequality (12) corresponds to a purely frictional fibre matrix bond with G_{π} set at zero.

If the conditions are such that the strain applied to the composite is just sufficient for matrix cracking to be energetically possible, it is apparent that this can be suppressed and caused to occur at a higher strain value by increased γ_m , decreasing the fibre thickness or by changing other parameters given in inequalities (11) and (12). Experimental observations of matrix crack suppression as a consequence of a reduction in fibre thickness have been reported by Cooper and Sillwood (2).

Matrix Cracks of Finite Length.

The analysis outlined above has been concerned with the amount of energy released and absorbed by the presence of a portion of a parallel sided crack. More recently an approximate analysis of the strain field existing around a crack of finite length in a reinforced composite has been considered by Morley and McColl (3), (4) and (5). The analysis has been confined to the behaviour of a composite reinforced with parallel uniformly spaced continuous fibres aligned in the direction of tensile loading and containing a transverse matrix crack. In order to simplify the computation linear strain distributions are considered and, as a first step, an approximate form of the strain distribution around a crack in the unreinforced matrix is defined.

The material is assumed to be loaded in uniaxial tension under fixed grip conditions and initially is experiencing everywhere a constant tensile strain ϵ_3 . When a crack of length $2a$ is placed in the material elastic relaxation takes place within an elliptical zone around the crack. This is assumed to take the form described in Figure 1 where the magnitude of the local elastic strain ϵ is plotted vertically. The diagram shows one half of the partially relaxed elliptical zone, the external load being applied in the x direction. The elastic strain carried by the material is zero at the crack faces and is assumed to increase linearly to the edge of the elliptical zone as indicated. The size of the zone is chosen so that the amount of strain energy released, for the idealised situation considered, is numerically equal to the value obtained by integrating the strain field around the crack derived from classical elasticity theory. The latter is numerically equivalent to the complete relaxation of an elliptical zone having an area in the plane of the material equal to twice that of a circle having the crack as its diameter. It follows that, for the idealised condition described in Figure 1, the major axis of the ellipse is three times the crack length.

When crack bridging reinforcing members are present, the strain field shown in Figure 1 is modified. In the model considered by Morley and McColl the stress transfer between the matrix and fibres is assumed to take place by frictional effects and the energy required to rupture any chemical bonding of the interface is assumed to be zero. It follows that the strain distribution along a reinforcing member from the position of the crack to

Figure 1. Assumed strain distribution around a crack in the unreinforced matrix.

Figure 2. Strain distribution along a reinforcing fibre.

the edge of the elliptical zone will be as illustrated in Figure 2. Here the crack is positioned at 0 and the edge of the elliptical zone is indicated by L_3 . The maximum load carried by the fibre and hence the maximum fibre strain occurs at the crack and is given by ϵ_μ where $\epsilon_\mu < \epsilon_{f,ult}$ the fibre failing strain. Load is transferred from the fibre to the matrix in the vicinity of the crack (from 0 to L_1 in Figure 2). The rate of change of fibre strain is thus,

$$d\epsilon_f/dx = -2\tau/E_f r \quad (13)$$

Over a distance dx the change in load carried by the fibres per unit cross sectional area of the composite structure is given by,

$$d\sigma_f V_f = (-2\tau/r) V_f dx \quad (14)$$

This change in load is transferred to the matrix giving a change in matrix strain $d\epsilon_m$. Hence,

$$d\epsilon_m/dx = 2V_f\tau/E_m V_m r + \epsilon_3/L_3 \quad (15)$$

The last term in equation (15) represents the rate of change in matrix strain which would be present in the unreinforced matrix and ϵ_3 is the general tensile strain carried by the composite outside the elliptical zone surrounding the crack. L_3 is the perpendicular distance from the face of the crack to the edge of the elliptical zone and is given by, $L_3 = 3(a^2 - y^2)^{1/2}$, where "a" is the half crack length and "y" is the distance from the centre of the crack to the composite section considered.

At the position L_1 the tensile strains in fibre and matrix are the same and no further stress transfer takes place. The strain in both fibres and matrix is assumed to remain constant from L_1 to L_2 . From the position L_2 , which lies on the strain distribution for the unreinforced matrix, to the edge of the elliptical zone the strain distributions in both fibres and matrix are assumed to be the same and to correspond to that of the unreinforced matrix.

Since the perturbations in the strain field generated by the matrix crack are assumed to be confined to the elliptical zone defined above, the increase in the length of the fibre near the crack must be balanced by the reduction in its length resulting from the decrease in fibre tensile strain elsewhere. Hence, the areas of the triangles shown shaded in Figure 2 must be equal.

This boundary condition together with equations (13) and (15) enables equations defining the strain distribution along any fibre and the surrounding matrix to be obtained. These are:

$$\epsilon_r = \{\epsilon_3 L_3 / [\Omega(P + \epsilon_3/L_3)^{-2} + L_3/\epsilon_3]\}^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

$$\epsilon_\mu = L_1(P + Q + \epsilon_3/L_3) \quad (17)$$

$$L_1 = \epsilon_r (P + \epsilon_3/L_3)^{-1} \quad (18)$$

$$L_2 = L_3 \epsilon_r / \epsilon_3 \quad (19)$$

$$L_3 = 3(a^2 - y^2)^{1/2} \quad (20)$$

Figure 3. Development of the strain field with increasing crack length.

where $P = 2V_f \tau / E_m V_m r$ and $Q = 2\tau / E_f r$. $\epsilon_r, \epsilon_\mu, \epsilon_3, L_1, L_2, L_3$ are defined in Figure 2.

The strain distributions in the vicinity of the crack both in the matrix and in the crack bridging fibres can thus be derived. In Figure 3 they are illustrated for an arbitrary composite structure as the crack length "a" increases from an arbitrary value of 0.3 units to 4.0 units. One quadrant of the ellipse is shown, the strain values being indicated by the vertical axis. It is apparent that, as the crack length increases, the stress transfer length between the crack bridging fibres and the matrix becomes smaller in relation to the size of the elliptical zone around the crack. Providing the failing strain $\epsilon_{f,ult}$ is not exceeded the rate of release of strain energy approaches some upper limiting value as the crack length becomes large compared with the fibre/matrix stress transfer length. This is discussed at greater length below.

The half crack opening at a distance y from the centre of the crack is obtained from the difference in integrated strain between the reinforcing fibres and the matrix over the distance OL_1 and is given by,

$$\mu = \epsilon_\mu L_1 / 2 \quad (21)$$

The strain energy, δWR_y , released by a parallel-sided section of the composite of width δy and unit thickness at a distance y from the centre of the crack, may be obtained from equations (16) to (20). Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta WR_y = & \{ E_c \epsilon_3^2 L_3 / 2 - E_c \epsilon_3^2 (L_3^3 - L_2^3) / 6L_3^2 \\ & - E_c \epsilon_r^2 (L_2 - L_1) / 2 - V_m E_m \epsilon_r^2 L_1 / 6 \\ & - V_f E_f (\epsilon_\mu^2 + \epsilon_\mu \epsilon_r + \epsilon_r^2) L_1 / 6 \} \delta y \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $E_c = E_m V_m + E_f V_f$.

The total strain energy released by the presence of the matrix crack can be computed by numerically integrating equation (22) over the whole of the elliptical zone. The rate of release of strain energy with increasing crack length can then be computed by numerical differentiation of the strain energy released at increasing crack lengths.

The work done against frictional forces during the growth of the crack can be computed in the following manner. First, a fibre located at a distance y from the mid-point of the crack is considered. During crack growth, relative displacements between the fibre and the matrix occur between the crack face and the position L_1 (Figure 2), so that the frictional energy losses are confined to this region.

The relative displacement dm_x at a distance x from the crack face is given by the integrated strain difference between the fibre and matrix from the position x to L_1 . Now $\epsilon_\mu (1 - x/L_1)$ is the strain difference between fibre and matrix at a distance x from the crack face so that:

$$\begin{aligned} dm_x &= \int_x^{L_1} \epsilon_\mu (1 - x/L_1) dx \\ &= \epsilon_\mu (L_1/2 - x + x^2/2L_1) \end{aligned}$$

where ϵ_μ and L_1 are given by equations (16) to (20). The frictional force across a length dx of the fibre/matrix interface will be given by $2\pi r dx$. Hence, the frictional work done by the length dx of the fibre at a distance x from the crack face during the growth of the crack is given by,

$$2\pi r dx dx_m = 2\pi r dx \epsilon_\mu (L_1/2 - x + x^2/2L_1)$$

The total work done by the fibre is obtained by integrating this expression from 0 to L_1 and is

$$\pi r \epsilon_\mu L_1^2/3.$$

The number of fibres in a section of width δy and unit thickness is $V_f \delta y / \pi r^2$. Hence the work done against frictional forces in this section of the quadrant of the ellipse is given by,

$$\delta W_{A_y} = V_f \tau \epsilon_\mu L_1^2 \delta y / 3r.$$

Substituting for ϵ_μ from equation (16) gives,

$$\delta W_{A_y} = V_f \tau \delta y \{P + Q + \epsilon_3 / L_3\} L_1^3 / 3r \quad (23)$$

The total strain energy absorbed frictionally can be obtained by numerically integrating equation (23) over the whole partially relaxed elliptical zone around the crack. The rate of absorption of energy with increasing crack length can then be obtained by numerically differentiating the strain energy absorbed frictionally at different crack lengths.

The energy released as a crack grows in size to a length $2a$ can be written $W_R(2a)$, the energy absorbed frictionally during crack growth $W_f(2a)$ and the work done in fracturing the matrix $2a G_m V_m$. Here G_m denotes the work of fracture of the matrix and V_m the volume fraction of the matrix. Hence, the critical crack length for instability occurs when,

$$dW_R(2a)/da = dW_f(2a)/da + 2G_m V_m$$

The rate of release of strain energy is greater than the rate of energy absorption by frictional effects so that when the matrix work of fracture G_m is very low transverse crack growth can occur at low stress values.

McColl and Morley have calculated the rates of release and absorption of energy with increasing transverse crack length for a composite system consisting of an epoxy resin matrix reinforced with a unidirectional array of stainless steel wire at the low volume fraction of 1.26% (5). In Figure 4 the relationship between the rate of release and absorption of energy and the value of the matrix work of fracture is illustrated for this system. The value of G_m in Figure 4 is taken as 0.26 KJm^{-2} . The diagram shows that, as the length of the matrix crack increases, the crack bridging fibres exert an increasing effect on the rate of release of strain energy. This approaches a constant value provided the fibres are capable of supporting the entire load carried by the composite. Also the effective work of fracture increases with increasing crack length. This is due to the increasing amount of strain energy absorbed by frictional effects as a consequence of differential movement between fibres and matrix. However it is also clear that when G_c , the intrinsic work of fracture of the matrix, is small the critical length for unstable crack growth is also small. For the particular value of G_c illustrated in Figure 4 the critical crack length is 40mm for a composite tensile strain value of 0.0015 and 16mm for a strain value of 0.002.

Figure 4. Rates of release and absorption of strain energy.

Figure 5. Relationship between critical crack length and matrix work of fracture.

It is clear from Figure 4 that the critical matrix crack length is very dependent on the matrix work of fracture. In Figure 5 the critical length for a transverse matrix crack in this particular system is shown plotted against the tensile strain carried by the composite for various values of G_c . These range from $\sim 0.05 \text{ KJm}^{-1}$ to $\sim 0.5 \text{ KJm}^{-1}$, the lower value corresponding approximately to the work of fracture of a typical ceramic material. The strain values of 0.1% to 0.2% indicated in Figure 5 are comparable with those experienced in engineering structures.

Hybrid Fibrous Composites.

The analysis predicts a strong link between the crack sensitivity and the work of fracture of the matrix. McColl and Morley have carried out a preliminary investigation of the effect of a second fibrous component used primarily to increase the work of fracture of the matrix (5). A small volume fraction ($V_f \approx 0.015$) of glass fibres was added to the polymer matrix. The orientation of these fibres was approximately random in the plane of the sheet and did not affect appreciably the elastic modulus of the composite in the loading direction by comparison with the similar volume fraction of aligned steel wires which were also used. The work of fracture of the matrix G_c was however increased by an order of magnitude by the presence of the glass fibres. The stress at which a transverse crack of a given length (40mm) propagated was increased by about three times as a consequence of the increased work of fracture value. Since the composite elastic modulus was not changed significantly by the glass fibres the strain energy density in the composite at the onset of matrix crack extension was increased by an order of magnitude by the presence of the glass fibres. The experimentally observed critical stress values were also found to be in reasonable agreement with the predictions of the theory.

Conclusions.

An analysis of the mechanics of transverse matrix crack extension in fibrous composites has been developed and this has enabled some aspects of composite behaviour to be predicted. It is apparent from Figures 4 and 5 that, when the work of fracture of the matrix of a fibrous composite is very small, the strain value at which crack extension occurs may not be strongly dependent on the volume fraction of the reinforcing fibres. For these conditions matrix cracking can be more effectively suppressed through the use of a second, matrix toughening, fibrous component. The two fibre groups inhibit transverse matrix crack growth in quite separate ways. Some of the predictions of the theory are supported by a limited amount of experimental data.

The effects of one fibrous component interact with those of the other and further studies are required before more general predictions can be made. However, it is clear that hybrid composites of this type offer a new approach to the problems of crack growth in brittle matrix systems.

It will be of interest to study the behaviour of hybrid systems of this type under cyclic loading and it may prove, by analogy with metal alloys, that fairly closely defined volume fractions of different types of fibres may be required to produce optimum properties in the composite structure.

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